

Child Trafficking and Sale of Children

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Abstract

This paper expresses the reason and root cause for the trade of children. The traffickers migrate the children illegally mainly for sexual exploitation, Forced marriage, Forced labours and Domestic servants. It's all about molestation. The Children are severely under paid and abused most of the times. Every year hundreds of children are trafficked approximately from the rural areas to the urban areas. Accordingly to the root causes for the child trafficking are poverty, lack of education for both parents and children & unemployment status. This paper provides the preventive measures to be taken to control trade of child to create a better tomorrow.

Keywords: Exploitation, Molestation, Trade of Children.

Introduction

Children are mainly trafficked for illegal activities, commercial sex etc. More vulnerable activities such as organ trade, begging etc are done by the traffickers. Organ trade is the most common thing next to commercial sex when traffickers force them to give up their organs. Children are forced to commercial sex for child pornography and child prostitution.

According to section 294 and 509 of Indian Penal Code (IPC) prohibit any individual or group of people pass any kind of offensive comment or execute any such gesture towards a girl of any age. According to Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1927, prohibits a girl (not only for girl child) who is not 18 age (defined by the Hindu Marriage Act) to get married. Central Government passed the ordinance to amend the POSCO Act to perform to grant the death penalty for the rape of children below 12 years though so many acts has been passed for the welfare of the children there are still the child trafficking happens. we know that it is an anti social activity but we don't have any methods/steps to detect them because they are happening at private places where there is no public enforcement.

Definition

The Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children, supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (informally known as the ‘Palermo Protocol’) is the first legal instrument to provide an internationally agreed definition of trafficking in human beings and child trafficking.

The ‘Palermo Protocol’ was adopted in 2000 and entered into force in 2003. With regard to child trafficking, it is clear that no violence, deception or coercion is required for a person under 18 to be considered a victim of trafficking; it is sufficient that he or she has been recruited and moved for the purpose of exploitation. Article 3 of the Protocol states that “the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of a child for the purpose of exploitation shall be considered “trafficking in persons” even if this does not involve any of the means set forth in sub-paragraph of this article.” Exploitation includes prostitution and other forms of sexual exploitation, harmful work, being forced to work, slavery, forcing people to do illegal or criminal things and the removal of organs. The definition applies to all people, men, women and children. But when it comes to children, any kind of recruitment, transportation, moving them around, buying or selling them or keeping them for the purpose of exploitation will be considered ‘trafficking’ –no matter how it is done.

This definition implies an understanding that a child cannot consent to being trafficked, and that a child’s ‘consent’ is not recognized as a justification for any form of child exploitation or abuse. Also, the above definition clearly spells out that trafficking covers not only the transportation of a person from one place to another, but also their recruitment and receipt so that anyone involved in the movement of another person for their exploitation is part of the trafficking process. It further articulates that trafficking is not limited to sexual exploitation only for it could occur also for forced labour and other slavery like practices. This means that people who migrate for work in agriculture, construction or domestic work, but are deceived or coerced into working in conditions they do not agree to, are also defined as trafficked people.

The definition of child trafficking in the Palermo Protocol is complex and can be difficult to apply in practice. It may be challenging to differentiate between a child victim of trafficking and a child who has experienced other forms of exploitation or abuse. This is especially the case when exploitation and abuse take place in the context of movement or migration and when the available information on a child’s situation and background is incomplete. In the absence of a uniform system for identifying children who are survivors of various forms of exploitation and abuse, trafficked children are often misidentified. They may be identified as migrant children, immigrants with irregular status, victims of sexual exploitation and abuse, juvenile delinquents or children living on the street. At the same time, not all children identified as having been trafficked have actually had experiences that fall under the international definition of child trafficking. Therefore, the way in which cases are identified and recorded in national statistics may not reflect the full scope of child trafficking.

Even children may be hesitant to be identified as trafficking victims. They may fear threats from traffickers against themselves or their family members, social stigma or legal consequences. Children may have concerns that once identified as having been trafficked, they will not be able to make money, pay off their debts or live up to the expectations their families have of them.

All those who contribute to the movement of the child and know that what they are doing is likely to lead to the exploitation of the child are traffickers. In this way, recruiters, intermediaries, document providers, corrupt officials, employers, exploiters and transporters are traffickers.

Objectives

- To analyse the main reason for child trafficking
- To give the solution (in my point of view) for the children’s welfare for the betterment of future.

Causes of Child Trafficking

The problem of child trafficking is the result of a constellation of factors, including widespread poverty, lack of livelihood opportunities, entrenched gender discrimination, displacement, the demand for young girls, the upheaval associated with natural disasters/conflict in parts of the country and the profits to be made. In some cases, socio-cultural and religious factors have an impact on child trafficking, as where religious figures have made use of their position to traffic girls for prostitution. Additional risk factors include, for example, parent illiteracy, illness or death of one of the main family breadwinners, unemployment, early school drop-out of the concerned children, absence of workplace inspection or policing, and a specific demand for child labour. Frequently, trafficking is accomplished through the deception of girls and their families. In many villages in West Bengal it is reported that traffickers have obtained access to girls by pretending to be grooms without dowry demands. In other cases, trafficking has been facilitated by relatives or friends of the victims, as well as teachers and placement agencies. The traffickers also exploit lack of political will by governments to tackle trafficking and its root causes. Moreover, girls who have been exploited are also commonly used to lure girls from source areas.

Also, increasing breakdown of social structures (which results in a loss of family and community support networks, making families, particularly women and children, increasingly vulnerable to traffickers demands and threats); Globalization and economic disparities between countries, and porous borders facilitates easy movement of people and large-scale illegal migration of women and children into India from the neighbouring countries and this illegal migration are exploited by the traffickers to traffic women and children into exploitative situations, including prostitution and labour

The Problem of Child Trafficking in India

Although it is often difficult to obtain comprehensive data on the extent of human trafficking in India, it is generally accepted that India is a source, destination, and transit country for trafficking of persons, including young girls. A 2006 study found that 378 of the 593 districts were affected by human trafficking. It is estimated that ninety percent of trafficking in the country is internal, with victims of trafficking mostly being used for forced labour. Child victims of trafficking in India are exploited in many ways – including factory and agricultural workers, domestic servants and beggars. Girls, in particular, are vulnerable to trafficking for the purpose of forced marriage and commercial sexual exploitation.

The porous borders in the region are often cited as a contributing factor to cross-border trafficking, including the trafficking of girls from Nepal and Bangladesh to India. ECPAT International estimates that 150,000 women and children are trafficked from South Asia annually, most from, through or to India. The combined estimates for Nepal and Bangladesh range from 500 to 10,000 girls being trafficked to India annually; another estimate puts the figure at more than 200,000 over a period of seven years. At present, there are no laws governing the repatriation of trafficking victims from India to Bangladesh and Nepal and concerned organizations have sought to assist girls in reaching their homes by liaising with partner organizations in these countries.

Crossing the border between Bangladesh and West Bengal is a daily routine for many. A well-organized bribe system also helps people to cross over the flat terrain. Further, a multiple passport system facilitates easy entry of Bangladeshi girls into Kolkata brothels and a close nexus exists between traffickers and border village communities'. After being sorted and graded', [girls] may be sold to pimps or sent to the Middle East, Kolkata, Bashirghat, Delhi, Mumbai or Agra". -Sen and P.M. Nair, A Report on Trafficking in Women and Children in India 2002-2003, Volume 1, Institute of Social Sciences, National Human Rights Commission and UNIFEM (2004).

International Instruments Signed by Government of India

The Government of India signed the Trafficking Protocol on 12 December 2002. This is a huge step forward in advancing the human rights of trafficked people as it not only prevents and protects the victims of trafficking but also punishes the traffickers. It has also ratified the 1949 Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic of Persons and of the Exploitation of the Prostitution of Others, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) and the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), all of which have been ratified by the Government of India. The Government of India has also ratified the two Optional Protocols to the Convention on the Rights of the Child – (i) on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflicts and (ii) on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography. The Convention on Preventing and Combating Trafficking in Women and Children for Prostitution devised by the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) in 2002, which has also defined the term ‘trafficking’, has also been ratified by the Government of India.

Law Enforcement in India

The various efforts undertaken by Indian Government to combat the problem of child trafficking are based on the Report of the Central Advisory Committee on Child Prostitution, the recommendations of the National Commission for Women and the directions of the Supreme Court of India as well as the experiences of various non-governmental organizations working in this area. The Ministry of Women and Child Development, the Nodal Ministry in the Government of India dealing with issues concerning women and children drew up a National Plan of Action to Combat Trafficking and Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Women and Children in the year 1998. The Ministry of Women and Child Development has requested all Secretaries of the Department of Women and Child Development in the States and Union Territories to hold regular meetings of State Advisory Committee constituted under the 1998 National Plan of Action to Combat Trafficking and Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Women and Children and monitor initiatives being undertaken by them with regard to prevention, rescue, rehabilitation, reintegration and repatriation of victims of trafficking. The Ministry of Women and Child Development has also undertaken a study in collaboration with UNICEF on Rescue and Rehabilitation of Child Victims Trafficked for Commercial Sexual Exploitation. The Report of this study was released to the public in 2005. It has also formulated a Protocol for Pre-Rescue, Rescue and Post-Rescue Operations of Child Victims of Trafficking for Commercial Sexual Exploitation. This Protocol contains guidelines for State Governments and a strategy for Rescue Team Members for pre-rescue, rescue and post-rescue operations concerning children who are victims of trafficking and were sexually being exploited for commercial reasons.

In September 2006, the Indian government responded to the trafficking issue by creating a central anti-trafficking law enforcement “nodal cell.” The nodal cell is a federal two-person department responsible for collecting and performing analysis of data related to trafficking, identifying the causes of the problem, monitoring action taken by state governments, and holding meetings with state-level law enforcement. In 2007, three state governments established anti-trafficking police units, the first of this kind in the India. In October 2006, the central government passed a law banning the employment of children in domestic work. In July 2006, the Maharashtra government was given authority by the Supreme Court to seal brothels. In March, 2008 Ministry of Labour & Employment has also issued a Protocol on Prevention, Rescue, Repatriation and Rehabilitation of Trafficked & Migrant Child Labour. In addition to this Ministry has also issued guidelines in 2010 to all the State Governments/UTs administrations on regulation of functioning of private placement agencies. Many State Governments have made provisions for registration of private placement agencies under Shops & Establishments Act.

In 2006, for the entire country, only 27 convictions for trafficking offenses were reported. From October 2006 to December 2006, 1672 child labour violations were reported, but no one was criminally prosecuted. Also in 2006, 685 suspected sex traffickers were detained, but no convictions were reported. Two specific examples given in the Trafficking in Persons report pertain to rescue missions. In New Delhi, 234 children were rescued by police from embroidery factories and rice mills. The owners of these businesses did not receive punishment. Forty-three government-run rescue missions freed 275 victims of commercial sex trafficking, however the government did not report any convictions on those accounts as well. As per inputs provided by National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), the total number of cases registered under different provisions of law which come under the generic description of human trafficking during the period 2009, 2010 and 2011 were 2848, 3422 and 3517 respectively. One reason for the registration of less number of cases can be the connivance of officials of high ranking with the traffickers for personal gain. Recently, one such incidence was reported in December 2012, in which a police officer was also suspended.

Moreover, Criminal sanctions against human trafficking are often too lenient, scattered across many different laws and largely underutilized by the State Government in the areas worst affected by trafficking. NGOs and human rights activists are left to fill the void of the government’s negligence. Without a significant amount of funds, how much of an impact can NGOs have? Since the crisis is too big, the Indian government must step up and address this issue. The lack of specific and/or adequate legislation on trafficking at the national level has been identified as one of the major obstacles in the fight against trafficking. There is an urgent need to harmonize legal definitions, procedures and cooperation at the national and regional levels in accordance with international standards. The passage of unified, comprehensive legislation on human trafficking could be a platform for significant progress in the awareness of public officials. It could also serve as a clear tool for use by NGOs and human rights activists.

Conclusion

Addressing human trafficking truly requires a comprehensive and multi-faceted strategy, which includes efforts aimed at the rehabilitation and social reintegration of trafficked victims. Otherwise, the strategy will not be successful in the long run. In essence, at the very core of any anti-trafficking strategy must be an unwavering commitment from individual countries and other multilateral actors to address human trafficking at every stage of this cycle, from prevention to recruitment, transportation to bonded labour, and from rescue to reintegration. Without this commitment, anti-trafficking efforts will be fundamentally unable to intervene on behalf of the trafficked victims whose human rights violations form the backbone of this exploitative trade.

Also, the enactment of the law on paper with no real training and support to the functionaries would be futile and therefore, what is needed now is “actual”, “planned” and “effective” implementation. Involving the community participation in the whole implementation process would create a greater impact. The procedures and technicalities should not reduce the ambitious legislations to empty words, because at stake here is the children- the future of the nation.

“Governments have to do more to guarantee children and young people their right to protection from trafficking. There is hope, and real and practical solutions exist. Trafficking of children for sexual purposes happens in virtually every country in the world - developed and developing - and we must see governments uphold their commitments to those solutions.”-Carmen M Madrinan.